

Evaluation of CMIP5-6 global climate models in the Arctic and Antarctic regions, atmosphere and surface ocean

Cécile Agosta, Christoph Kittel, Charles Amory,
Tamsin Edwards, and Cécile Davrinche

EGU General Assembly 2022

CR1.2 Ice sheet mass balance and sea level: ISMASS/ISMIP6 and beyond

This presentation is part of the AWACA project that has received funding from the European Research Council (ERC Synergy) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme (Grant agreement No 951596)

This presentation is part of the PROTECT project that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme (Grant agreement No 869304).

Atmosphere, a major forcing of ice sheet models

Objective:
Assessment of CMIP models large scale fields over polar regions
→ First overview, to be combined with further analyses

Ice sheet atmosphere forcing:

- Snow accumulation
- Surface air temperature
- Surface melt

→ Depend on **large-scale climate**
(+ clouds + boundary layer processes)

Biases at present impact projections (e.g. sea ice)
E.g. Bracegirdle et al. 2015
Spatial bias patterns are stationary
Krinner & Flanner 2018

**ERA5 annual
700hPa air temp. (°C)
1979-2005**

Atmosphere, a major forcing of ice sheet models

Objective:

Assessment of CMIP models large scale fields over polar regions
→ First overview, to be combined with further analyses

Method :

- 1979-2005 time-mean
- Annual or Seasonal
- Difference with ERA5
- 2 regions

Exemple for one CMIP model : IPSL-CM6A-LR

Temperature

Humidity

Circulation

Surface ocean

Atmosphere, a major forcing of ice sheet models

Method :

- 1979-2005 time-mean
- Annual or Seasonal
- Difference with ERA5
- 2 regions

**9 variables, different units/scales:
how to combine them?**

- T700 [annual]
- T700 [summer]
- T850 [annual]
- T850 [summer]
- Integrated water vapor [annual]
- Z500 [annual]
- Sea level pressure [annual]
- SST [summer]
- Sea ice cover [winter]

Temperature

Humidity

Circulation

Surface ocean

Atmosphere, a major forcing of ice sheet models

**9 variables, different units/scales:
how to combine them?**

And for each variable...

- Method :**
- 1979-2005 time-mean
 - Annual or Seasonal
 - Difference with ERA5
 - 2 regions

CMIP evaluation: **Relative metrics**

9 variables
83 CMIP models
2 regions

First method : **Relative metrics**

Scaling of metrics to combine them among variables

Agosta et al. 2015; Barthel et al. 2020 (ISMIP6), ESMValTool (e.g. Eyring et al. 2020)

IPSL-CM6A-LR
 $\Delta T_{850}[\text{ann}]$

$$\text{RMSE } (^{\circ}\text{C}) = \sqrt{\text{spatial mean}(\Delta^2)}$$

→ **Scaled-RMSE = RMSE / Median RMSE among all CMIP models**

CMIP evaluation: **Relative metrics**

9 variables
83 CMIP models
2 regions

First method : **Relative metrics**
Scaling of metrics to combine them among variables

Agosta et al. 2015; Barthel et al. 2020 (ISMIP6), ESMValTool (e.g. Eyring et al. 2020)

IPSL-CM6A-LR
 $\Delta T_{850}[\text{ann}]$

$$\text{RMSE } (^{\circ}\text{C}) = \sqrt{\text{spatial mean}(\Delta^2)}$$

→ **Scaled-RMSE = RMSE / Median RMSE among all CMIP models**

Score: mean Scaled-RMSE among variables

Results: CMIP models for both the Arctic & the Antarctic

Score: mean Scaled-RMSE among variables

Results: CMIP models for both the Arctic & the Antarctic

Score: mean Scaled-RMSE among variables

28 (34 %) CMIP models in the « best half » for both regions
9 CMIP5, 19 CMIP6 (25% of CMIP5 vs. 40% of CMIP6)

CMIP evaluation: **Relative metrics**

9 variables
83 CMIP models
2 regions

IPSL-CM6A-LR
 $\Delta T_{850}[\text{ann}]$

Second method : **Implausible fraction**
Absolute metric, **No scaling**

History matching, « Not Ruled Out Yet » method (Pukelsheim, 1994, Rougier, 2015), applied e.g. in Gladstone et al. 2012; Edwards et al., 2019

5 % implausible

40 % implausible

Hashes: $\Delta > 3 \text{ std}_{1\text{yr}}(\text{reference})$

Portion of the surface where Δ with ERA5 is **greater than 3 x ERA5 interannual variability** = « **Implausible fraction** » of the surface

CMIP evaluation: Relative metrics

9 variables
83 CMIP models
2 regions

IPSL-CM6A-LR
 $\Delta T_{850}[\text{ann}]$

Second method : **Implausible fraction**
Absolute metric, **No scaling**

History matching, « Not Ruled Out Yet » method (Pukelsheim, 1994, Rougier, 2015), applied e.g. in Gladstone et al. 2012; Edwards et al., 2019

Hashes: $\Delta > 3 \text{ std}_{1\text{yr}}(\text{reference})$

Portion of the surface where Δ with ERA5 is **greater than 3 x ERA5 interannual variability** = « **Implausible fraction** » of the surface

Score: 2nd max implausible fraction
(We let 1 variable / 9 be more implausible)

Arctic (> 50°N)

2nd max
Implausible
fraction

Mean Scaled RMSE

Antarctic (< 40°S)

2nd max
Implausible
fraction

Mean Scaled RMSE

Arctic (> 50°N)

Antarctic (< 40°S)

2nd max Implausible fraction

Mean Scaled RMSE

2nd max Implausible fraction

Mean Scaled RMSE

• CMIP models are **more implausible in the Antarctic** than in the Arctic

Arctic (> 50°N)

Best half

Mean Scaled RMSE

Antarctic (< 40°S)

Best half

Mean Scaled RMSE

- CMIP models are **more implausible in the Antarctic** than in the Arctic
- **Same « Best half »** for Scaled RMSE and Implausibility

Arctic (> 50°N)

2nd max
Implausible
fraction

Best half

Mean Scaled RMSE

Antarctic (< 40°S)

2nd max
Implausible
fraction

Best half

Mean Scaled RMSE

- CMIP models are **more implausible in the Antarctic** than in the Arctic
- **Same « Best half »** for Scaled RMSE and Implausibility
- « Best half » contains **both CMIP5 and CMIP6 models**

Atmosphere, a major forcing of ice sheet models

Objective:
Assessment of CMIP models large scale fields over polar regions
→ First overview, to be combined with further analyses

Ice sheet atmosphere forcing:

- Snow accumulation
- Surface air temperature
- Surface melt

→ Depend on **large-scale climate**
(+ clouds + boundary layer processes)

Biases at present impact projections (e.g. sea ice)
E.g. Bracegirdle et al. 2015
Spatial bias patterns are stationary
Krinner & Flanner 2018

**ERA5 annual
700hPa air temp. (°C)
1979-2005**

CMIP evaluation: Relative metrics

9 variables
83 CMIP models
2 regions

First method : **Relative metrics**
Scaling of metrics to combine them among variables

Agosta et al. 2015; Barthel et al. 2020 (ISMIP6), ESMValTool (REF)

Rank: mean Scaled-RMSE among variables

CMIP evaluation: Relative metrics

9 variables
83 CMIP models
2 regions

First method : **Relative metrics**
Scaling of metrics to combine them among variables

Agosta et al. 2015; Barthel et al. 2020 (ISMIP6), ESMValTool (REF)

Rank: mean Scaled-RMSE among variables

Scaled RMSE = 0 ⇒ Perfect model = ERA5

CMIP evaluation: Relative metrics

9 variables
83 CMIP models
2 regions

First method : **Relative metrics**
Scaling of metrics to combine them among variables

Agosta et al. 2015; Barthel et al. 2020 (ISMIP6), ESMValTool (REF)

Rank: mean Scaled-RMSE among variables

CMIP evaluation: Relative metrics

9 variables
83 CMIP models
2 regions

First method : **Relative metrics**
Scaling of metrics to combine them among variables

Agosta et al. 2015; Barthel et al. 2020 (ISMIP6), ESMValTool (REF)

Rank: mean Scaled-RMSE among variables

CMIP evaluation: Absolute metrics

9 variables
83 CMIP models
2 regions

Second method : **Absolute metric**
Implausible fraction, **No scaling**

Rank: 2nd max implausible fraction
(We let one variable be very implausible)

